

Making Safe the Buildings using the Internet of Things with the Fuzzy logic

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Abstract:- In this paper we have a model of change moisture monitoring in Temples and the historical Monuments. A system formed with the help of Internet of Things where we use sensors to measure how rain water, Ground water and humidity inside the building. Formed control model is uses fuzzy logic to take decisions how we can protect. Formed model makes an intelligent system for control the water paths inside and outside Temples and the historical Monuments. Formed system to be installed and monitored for better results. We are trying to install and form results how it can protect from the environmental can be protected in the Less Cost.

Keywords:- Historical Monuments, Humidity, Fuzzy Logic, Internet of Things.

I. INTRODUCTION

[1]Future computing technology will be waving beyond the traditional technology. IoT is among the top of the leading technologies, will be equipped with IoT. Blooming Technology RFID (radio frequency identification) and sensors it created to be with help of internet. The devices will create an environment with Cloud Computing gives infrastructure for visual platforms and use computing, which will integrate the devices with the monitoring, storage devices, client delivery, analytics and monitoring. Cloud computing will be the end-to-end service for users and businesses for on demand accessing the applications from any part of the world.[1]

The sensors can analyze obstacles that may be categorized as static or dynamic. Using the navigation system, the target can be located an minimum search [2] . Many IoT-based devices have advantages to be used with emerging technologies. Due to the Efficiency, compatibility, and consistency on a broad wide spread success of IoT. A combination of various technologies along with software can bring new hybrid system with applications in various fields of interest in communications [3][4]

A many studies taken on fuzzy logic to develop path tracking for water according to present and future path information, designing and implementation of path tracking in water inside environment, protect from obstacle by checking distance, and change in distance from the obstacle as input parameters. The output parameter in these cases is the check the obstacle. A comparison of obstacle avoidance by sensors with fuzzy logic monitoring. We can add, ultrasonic as well as infrared (IR) sensors to regularly check the rain water and humidity.

The system with the more ultrasonic sensors detects the water flow and gives signals to the monitor. When the water enters a certain path of the building or temple, a Bluetooth device connects and informs the monitor about its location. The model is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Temple or Historical Monument with Sensor

A system formed with the help of Internet of Things where we use sensors to measure how rain water, Ground water and humidity inside the building. Formed control model is uses fuzzy logic to take decisions how we can protect. . Formed model makes an intelligent system for control the water paths inside and outside Temples and the historical Monuments. Fuzzy logic Monitor is used to operate and monitor system. The outputs of the Ultra violet sensors are provided as inputs to the monitor and makes decision on the basis of protocols according to the information contained by the output of the sensors. The command from the Fuzzy logic Monitor is sent to devices for generating signals to navigate the user in a Temple or Historical Monument along with the paths of the water in the premises. The Fuzzy logic Monitor is shown in Figure 2.takes fuzzy of the inputs is done followed by Protocols and defined the protocols, and output is generated by the de-fuzzy of inputs using an interface.

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Fig 2. Block Diagram of Fuzzy Logic Monitor

II. CONCLUSION

Thus model for monitoring the Temples and the historical Monuments using the Internet of Things system is formed. The Internet of Things system having sensors produces signals about the water in the path and also navigates the user to move around premises. The outputs from the Internet of Things system are feed into Fuzzy Logic Controller. Thus, Formed model makes an intelligent system for control the water paths inside and outside Temples and the historical Monuments. Formed system to be installed and monitored for better results. We are trying to install and form results how it can protect from the environmental can be protected in the Less Cost.